

Reverse Decomposition Method vs Simplified Photovoltaic Module Electrical Model Comparison

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Abstract

The resolution of the Photovoltaic modules electrical mathematical models can be addressed in different ways. Depending on the degree of precision required, several options are available, which will require more or less computational resources in order to solve it. The simplified models have the advantage that they require less resources than the non-simplified ones. This is possible since some parameters are omitted. Their effect is consequently discarded. In this sense, the herein proposed Photovoltaic module implicit equation model resolution procedure allows to obtain the characteristic current voltage curves considering all the implied electrical parameters. Furthermore, it is proved that referred model, in comparison with the simplified one, evidences that this one is providing results with a low percentage of error.

Keywords: Photovoltaic. Reverse Decomposition, Numerical Methods

1. INTRODUCTION

A Photovoltaic (PV) module is an industrially assembled structure configured of an array with solar cells, which are series and parallel configured.

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The solar cells they are made of, are in essence p-n semiconductor based devices capable of generating electricity from the incident sunlight, by means of the PV process [1]. Since 1954, when the first efficient PV cells were manufactured, up to date, the technology has made possible to reach efficiencies in the surrounding of the 45% [2].

The electrical mathematical model of a PV module is a resourceful tool to understand and predict its behavior and calculate its performance. The modeling can be achieved in different ways, which have been for long deeply explained in the literature [3, 4, 5].

By means of referred models, the current-voltage (I-V) and power-voltage (P-V) PV module characteristic curves can be obtained, which figure-out the module fingerprint. These models allow obtaining results under different operating conditions, the so called *Standard Test Conditions* (STC), which correspond to an irradiance of 1000 W/m^2 , 25°C of cell temperature and Air Mass Index (AM) 1,5 and the *Real Operating Conditions* (ROC), which are the atmospheric conditions that the PV modules are submitted to. The comparative analysis of these results can explain the modules behaviors and the effect of ROC as well as the effect of PV module losses.

The resolution of referred models by means of applying computational resources can be time demanding of different considerations.

A one diode electrical mathematical extended model in the form of an implicit equation resolution procedure has been presented in [6].

The capability of model resolution in comparison with other simplified models proves not only its viability, but, furthermore, the error generated by the use of the simplified model is verified to be minimal. This paper is structured as follows: in section 2 a brief description is made of the PV module electrical model and of the main electrical operating parameters. In section 3, the Reverse Decomposition method is applied to the PV module characteristic equation. Then in section 4, its application to commercial PV modules and consequent results are described of the Reverse Decomposition Method. Finally in section 5, the different algorithms are described. The last section draws some conclusions.

2. PV MODULE ELECTRICAL AND MATHEMATICAL MODEL

When a PV module is being submitted to the sun irradiance, the PV process begins and starts generating electrons in movement to create the

electric current. An ideal PV module can be represented by an ideal photo-generated current source (I_{ph}) with two diodes in parallel [4, 7]. A simpler version considers only a single diode in parallel, as per Fig.1, [8, 9, 10]:

Fig.1 - Simplified model of the illuminated PV module

The PV module irradiated responds to the mathematical model of the following equation:

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+I \cdot R_s}{n \cdot N_s \cdot V_T}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V + I \cdot R_s}{R_p} \quad (1)$$

which defines the relationship between V and I that are respectively the voltage and current supplied by the PV module; I_{ph} stands for the photo-generated current; n is the diode ideality factor; N_s is the number of series connected cells of the PV module; V_T is the equivalent diode thermal voltage and R_p and R_s represent the PV module ohmic losses.

This model has the constraint that it results an implicit equation, which requires significant computational resources to solve it and to obtain the corresponding I-V and P-V PV module characteristic curves (Fig.2) and the five resulting operational parameters, including the Maximum Power Point (MPP).

These parameters are:

- I_{SC} : short circuit current ($V = 0V$)
- V_{OC} : open circuit voltage ($I = 0A$)
- V_{mp} : Voltage at MPP
- I_{mp} : Current at MPP

Fig.2 - I-V-P PV module characteristic curve and main electrical operating parameters

- P_{mp} : Power at MPP

Besides traditional computational environments, other possible solutions have been described in the literature. A solution based on the use of the Lambert W-function is described in [15]. Furthermore, in [6] it has been proposed the so-called Reverse Decomposition Method to solve the PV module implicit electrical model. This model has been applied in this case. In order to compare measured PV module operating parameters with the values that theoretically should be obtained, under the applying atmospheric conditions, a mathematical model of the PV module is required. There are several options that have already been referred in the literature. One of them is the two diodes model [11]; nevertheless, the single diode option despising R_p has been considered, which being accurate, significantly simplifies the model resolution [12, 13, 14] (Fig.3).

Accordingly, solving equation (1), we obtain:

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+I \cdot R_s}{n \cdot N_s \cdot V_T}} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

where the later equation (2) represents the non-implicit simplified mathematical one diode model of the illuminated PV module.

This equation is based on six variables, namely I , V , I_{ph} , I_0 , V_T and R_s . The PV module fingerprint I-V curve can be obtained by solving equation (2). This can be done any time because the values of I_{ph} , I_0 and V_T are known. It has been considered the option based on PV module manufacturers data sheets, as in [16]. This can apply to the photo-generated current (I_{ph}) and consequently to the PV module output voltage in absence of load, that is, the

Fig.3 - One diode electrical model of the PV cell with parasitic R_p and R_s resistances

open circuit PV module voltage (V_{OC}). Given all these data, finally, the PV module fingerprint I-V characteristic curve can be drawn. For this purpose, starting from equation (2) and solving for V, we obtain:

$$V = V_T \cdot n \cdot N_s \cdot \log \left(\frac{I_{ph} + I_0 - I}{I_0} \right) - I \cdot R_s \quad (3)$$

which can be solved for $I_{ph} = I_{SC}$. This equation will be used in order to determine the theoretical value of the PV module output voltage, for the range of current (I) between 0 ampere and I_{SC} [17].

Additionally, in order to evaluate the procedure under non STC, it has also been applied to ROC.

For this purpose, following translation equations have been applied for the PV module current and voltage parameters:

$$I_{SC_t} = I_{SC_o} \cdot \frac{G_e}{G_0} [1 + \alpha(T_m - T_0)] \quad (4)$$

$$V_{OC_t} = V_{OC_o} [1 + \beta(T_m - T_0)] \cdot \left[1 + \delta \cdot \log \left(\frac{G_e}{G_0} \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

where 0 subscript variables are the manufacturers data sheets STC referred ones; G is the irradiance in the plane of the module (in W/m^2); G_0 is the reference irradiance at STC ($1000 W/m^2$); α is the current temperature coefficient ($^{\circ}C^{-1}$); T_m is the module back-plane temperature; T_0 is the module temperature at STC; β is the voltage temperature coefficient ($^{\circ}C^{-1}$) and δ is the voltage irradiance temperature coefficient ($^{\circ}C^{-1}$).

3. REVERSE DECOMPOSITION METHOD. APPLICATION TO THE PV MODULE CHARACTERISTIC EQUATION

In order to solve these equations, Adam-Bashforth and Adam-Moulton methods philosophy have been applied. Given equation (1):

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+I \cdot R_S}{n \cdot N_s \cdot V_T}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V + I \cdot R_S}{R_p}$$

the variable V_p (voltage prediction) has been initially cleared from the explicit part of resulting equation after despising the last of the summands in previous equation.

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V_p+I \cdot R_S}{n \cdot N_s \cdot V_T}} - 1 \right) \quad (6)$$

Solving for V_p , it results:

$$V_p = V_T \cdot n \cdot N_s \cdot \log \left(\frac{I_{ph} + I_0 - I}{I_0} \right) - I \cdot R_S \quad (7)$$

Once V_p has been calculated, it is substituted in the full equation:

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V_C+I \cdot R_S}{n \cdot N_s \cdot V_T}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V_P + I \cdot R_S}{R_p} \quad (8)$$

Finally, clearing V_c (voltage correction) variable

$$V_c = V_T \cdot n \cdot N_s \cdot \log \left[\frac{I_{ph} + I_0 - \left(I + \frac{V_p+IR_S}{R_P} \right)}{I_0} \right] - I \cdot R_S \quad (9)$$

At this point, a loop is generated that will converge to the solution of the problem. The Reverse Decomposition Method has been developed for the general resolution of implicit equation (1). Initial procedure used is defined for its foundation.

- Considering a known constant c , an invertible function f and any other function g , being the general equation:

$$c = f(x) + g(x) \quad (10)$$

Where x cannot be cleared.

- Initially, we despise $g(x)$ and we obtain the initial value of x_0

$$c = f(x) \Rightarrow x = f^{-1}(c) \Rightarrow x_0 = x$$

- Coming back to the original equation, and substituting x in $g(x)$, which generates x_1 :

$$c = f(x) + g(x_0) \Rightarrow x = f^{-1}(c - g(x_0)) \Rightarrow x_1 = x$$

Developing this procedure successively, it results as follows:

Procedure 3.1 (Reverse Decomposition Method).

Given an equation in the form of $c = f(x) + g(x)$, we choose a precision $\epsilon > 0$ and then calculate an initial value $x_0 = f^{-1}(c)$. From this point, we calculate for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$x_n = f^{-1}(c - g(x_{n-1})) \text{ while } |x_n - x_{n-1}| \geq \epsilon$$

3.1. Convergence

We will proceed to see under what conditions this procedure converges.

Definition 3.2. *A function $f : D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be Lipschitzian function if there exists a constant $L > 0$ such that:*

$$|f(x_1) - f(x_2)| \leq L \cdot |x_1 - x_2| \quad \forall x_1, x_2 \in D$$

Constant L is so called Lipschitz constant and, if $L < 1$, the function f is so called contraction

Definition 3.3. *A function $f : D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be biLipschitz function [18] if there exist two constant L_1 y L_2 , greater than zero, such that:*

$$L_1 \cdot |x_1 - x_2| \leq |f(x_1) - f(x_2)| \leq L_2 \cdot |x_1 - x_2| \quad \forall x_1, x_2 \in D$$

Proposition 3.4. *All biLipschitz function is a Lipschitz function*

Proof

It is trivial, in the case that $L_2 = L$

Proposition 3.5. *Let $f : D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. If f' is bounded between two positive values in D then f is a biLipschitz function.*

Proof

Since f' is bounded between two positive values in D then

$$L_1 \leq f'(x) \leq L_2$$

and by mean value theorem, always exist an interval $(x_1, x_2) \in D, x_1 \neq x_2$ such that

$$L_1 \leq \frac{|f(x_1) - f(x_2)|}{|x_1 - x_2|} \leq L_2$$

and so multiplying all by $|x_1 - x_2|$

$$L_1 \cdot |x_1 - x_2| \leq |f(x_1) - f(x_2)| \leq L_2 \cdot |x_1 - x_2|$$

q.e.d.

Theorem 3.6. *For each couple of functions f and g where f is injective and revertible and g is biLipschitz, the Reverse Decomposition method converges to the solution of the problem*

$$c = f(x) + g(x)$$

Proof

In order to see if it converges to the problem solution, we must verify that if n grows then $|x_n - x_{n-1}|$ tends to zero, or also that x_{n-1} approaches x_n , when x_n reaches the solution.

We start from

$$x_n = f^{-1}\left(c - g(x_{n-1})\right)$$

When x_n approaches the solution of the problem, it must comply with the original equation and hence

$$c \simeq f(x_n) + g(x_n)$$

Substituting in the previous one, it remains

$$x_n \simeq f^{-1}\left(f(x_n) + g(x_n) - g(x_{n-1})\right)$$

Since f is injective there exists one value x_n such that $f^{-1}(f(x_n)) = x_n$, and considering that x_n itself complies, we have that $|g(x_n) - g(x_{n-1})|$ tends to zero.

Since g is a biLipschitz function, it exists $L_1 > 0$ such that

$$|g(x_n) - g(x_{n-1})| > L_1 \cdot |x_n - x_{n-1}|$$

Considering that $|g(x_n) - g(x_{n-1})|$ tends to zero and L_1 is constant, it complies that

$$L_1 \cdot |x_n - x_{n-1}| \rightarrow 0 \Rightarrow |x_n - x_{n-1}| \rightarrow 0 \Rightarrow x_{n-1} \rightarrow x_n$$

q.e.d.

The graphic representation of this procedure is expressed in the following Fig.4

Fig.4 - Representation of Reverse Decomposition Method

Once it has been demonstrated the conditions that Reverse Decomposition procedure must comply with, we proceed to apply it to the PV module equation. Required programming has been developed under CAS (Computer Algebra System) under wxMaxima and MatLab programs. A root solution is calculated of equation (1):

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+I \cdot R_s}{n \cdot N_s \cdot V_T}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V + I \cdot R_s}{R_p}$$

Taking $f(V) = I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+I \cdot R_s}{n \cdot N_s \cdot V_T}} - 1 \right)$ injective and $g(V) = \frac{V+I \cdot R_s}{R_p}$ a biLipschitz function in the surrounding of the solution (since the derivate $g'(V) = \frac{1}{R_p}$ is bounded between positive values for all V finite solution of the equation).

4. APPLICATION TO THE EQUATION OF COMMERCIAL PV MODULES. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Let us solve for two different conditions, STC and Translated to ROC; in this case, namely an incident irradiance $G = 810 \text{ W/m}^2$ and an ambient temperature $T_a = 21^\circ\text{C}$.

$$I_{ph} - I = f(V) + g(V) \quad (11)$$

Both procedures have been applied to Isofotón ISF-245 PV module, which main STC referred electrical parameters have been extracted from the manufacturers data sheets and summarized in Table I.

Electrical parameter	Value
Rated Power (Pmax)	245 W
Open-circuit Voltage (VOC)	37,3 V
Short-circuit Current (ISC)	8,70 A
Maximum power point Voltage (Vmax)	30,2 V
Maximum power point Current (Imax)	8,12 A
Efficiency	14,8%
Power tolerance (% Pmax)	+/-3%

Table I. Isofotón ISF-245 PV module data-sheet electrical parameters at STC

Table II summarizes the PV module electrical operational parameters for both the STC and the ROC options:

	PV module operating parameter	STC	ROC translated
I_{ph}	Photogenerated current	8,7	7,11
I_0	Diode reverse saturation current (A)	2,67e-10	5.31e-9
R_S	Series resistance (Ω)	0,4	0,35
R_P	Parallel resistance (Ω)	10e3	10e3
V_T	Thermal voltage (V)	0,026	0,027
N_S	Series connected cells	60	60
m	Diode ideality factor	1	1

Table II. STC and ROC PV modules electrical parameters

According to these parameters, and applying referred equations, the corresponding results are depicted in Fig.4 for both the implicit Reverse Decomposition Method and the non-implicit Simplified Model. The procedure has been applied to two different operating scenarios. One of them is the corresponding to STC. The other one applies to ROC. In Fig.5, it can be seen that either in STC or in ROC scenarios, the models follow the same curve shape with no divergence.

The I-V curve for the implicit equation proposed model at STC (blue line) runs in coincidence with the resulting applying the simplified model (red line). Furthermore, if we consider the ROC translated option, again both curves are similar. It can be seen that the resulting curve of the proposed model at ROC (green line) is almost coincident with the one corresponding to the simplified model (violet line).

In Fig.6, the percentage of error obtained with referred method for both implicit and non-implicit models are depicted. As it can be seen, the amount of error between both models can be considered almost negligible, since in the worst case (at low voltage values), it reaches the value of almost 0.2%. This demonstrates that the electrical model resolution by means of the proposed Reverse Decomposition procedure can be considered as an alternate option, being reliable, although additional computational resources demanding.

5. ANALYSIS OF ALGORITHMS

After making the calculations with the Reverse Decomposition method, they were compared with classical equations resolution procedures using Mat-

Fig.5. PV module I-V characteristic curve for the implicit model (blue line), for the simplified one (red line), both at STC and also at ROC implicit (green line) and simplified (violet line).

Lab. For this purpose, algorithms have been established and compared for four methods:

1. Method of Reverse Decomposition:
 - (a) General functions, dependent parameters, are created.
 - (b) Corresponding parameters are replaced and by means of Matlab the inverses are computed.
 - (c) The solution is approximated by the Reverse Decomposition method.
2. Method of Newton:
 - (a) General functions and replaced parameters are established; with MatLab, the derivative is calculated.
 - (b) The solution is approximated by Newton.
3. Quick method of Reverse Decomposition:
 - (a) Parameters dependent general functions and inverses are created.
 - (b) The solution is approximated by the Reverse Decomposition method.
4. Quick method of Newton:
 - (a) The parameters dependent general functions and their derivatives, are created.
 - (b) The solution is approximated by Newton.

Table III shows execution times (to calculate Fig.5 data) based on exact decimal number required. It can be seen that the proposed Quick Reverse

Fig.6. Error rate of proposed model vs simplified model in the I-V curves for the STC (blue line) and translated (red line) conditions

decomposition method is the fastest one, which requires fewer computational resources. Even better results than the Quick Newton method. This issue is much more evident in case of considering a large number of decimals. As an example, for 15 decimals, the Reverse Decomposition method algorithm requires 24.3 sec. of computer machine time to be solved, while the Newton method requires 153.6 sec. Meanwhile, the Quick Newton method reports better results for the same case, 18 sec. which are significantly reduced if the Quick Reverse method is applied, which reduces the elapsed time to almost 1.2 sec.; that is, almost 9 times faster. According to the obtained results, consequently, the quick Reverse Decomposition method has been used to solve the equations presented in this paper.

Decimals	Reverse	Newton	Quick Reverse	Quick Newton
1	19.7786	8.0578	0.5021	0.8692
2	19.7239	11.1768	0.5062	1.1774
3	19.9000	11.5197	0.5103	1.2299
4	20.2300	11.8203	0.5434	1.2047
5	21.8699	12.6025	0.8546	1.2856
6	21.9481	14.7760	0.8399	1.5613
7	22.1425	16.3530	1.0438	1.8676
8	25.0950	15.8374	0.8467	1.6645
9	22.9688	16.0406	0.8617	1.6660
10	22.4367	14.9560	0.8500	1.5808
11	23.0069	15.3835	0.9542	1.6455
12	23.8429	16.5730	1.1195	1.7718
13	23.9073	17.7176	1.1157	1.9091
14	24.2437	89.0650	1.1298	9.2302
15	24.3046	153.5667	1.1976	18.0286

Table III. Execution time of algorithms (in seconds)

6. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed Reverse Decomposition resolution method has been demonstrated to be suitable to precisely solve the implicit one diode model of the PV module. The comparison has been made of obtained results with those resulting from the solution applying the one diode simplified model without R_p parasitic resistance. The evidence is that the error made is less than 0.2% in the worst case. It is a matter of fact that the proposed method requires more powerful computational resources than the simplified one for its resolution. Nevertheless, it should be taken into account that it allows performing more detailed analysis of the PV module electrical model considering the impact due to the presence of the parasitic resistances, mainly R_p , which is generally neglected. It is worth noting that the proposed Quick Reverse method significantly reduces the computer machine time to resolve the implicit equation of the one diode PV module level. This improves the machine requirements for obtaining the I-V and P-V PV modules fingerprints. These procedures can be applied to the equation (1) considering both STC and ROC conditions. Resulting curves have been depicted and compared. As a result of such comparison, resulting error is almost insignificant.

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